

Methodological Framework for the ALISE Research Taxonomy Revision

ALISE Taxonomy Ad Hoc Committee Coleman, Anita S. (Chair) | Xiaohua A. Zhu | Tyler Youngman

Meeting Date Time: May 29, 2026, 12 noon Pacific Time / 3:00 PM Eastern (Zoom)

This document supplements: Coleman, Anita S. (2026). *Updating the ALISE Research Taxonomy*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20370505>

1. Purpose

This note documents the methodological framework adopted by the ALISE Taxonomy Ad Hoc Committee at its inaugural meeting on Friday, 29 May, 2026. It supplements the original proposal (Coleman, 2026) accepted by the ALISE Board in May 2026, and serves as the working methodology for producing a revised taxonomy for use at the 2027 ALISE Annual Conference.

2. Warrant Framework

Descriptor selection and revision will be governed by a hybrid warrant approach:

Bibliographic warrant forms the baseline; new or revised descriptors must be demonstrable through LIS conference themes, peer-reviewed journal keywords, or policy documents. This ensures every addition is grounded in documented scholarly use.

Cultural warrant, following Hope Olson's foundational work in knowledge organization, recognizes that taxonomies embed values and that marginalized perspectives, emerging fields, and global LIS research require explicit representation even where the dominant literature has not yet caught up. This warrant justifies equity-centered additions including DEI descriptors and global and indigenous LIS categories.

Community warrant is enacted through a two-phase feedback process: (1) structured review by chairs of all ALISE Special Interest Groups, and (2) open comment period for the full ALISE membership. Community warrant ensures the revised taxonomy reflects practitioner and educator knowledge, not only published scholarship.

3. Standards Basis

The revision is grounded in established controlled vocabulary and thesaurus construction standards:

- **ISO 25964** (Parts 1 and 2) – the international standard for thesauri for information retrieval and interoperability
- **ANSI/NISO Z39.19** – Guidelines for the Construction, Format, and Management of Monolingual Controlled Vocabularies

These standards govern scope note development, broader/narrower/related term relationships, preferred and non-preferred term references, and bibliographic warrant requirements for individual descriptors. It is our intention to include these, but this may be selective and skeletal, rather than full and complete.

4. Development Approach

The revision adopts a middle-out development approach; we will begin with the most productive intermediate level of the existing structure, expanding upward and downward as warranted. This is preferable to purely top-down (risks imposing structure) or purely bottom-up (risks losing coherence) approaches.

The revision retains the flat nine-area structure. The most substantive structural addition is Information History and Memory as a new primary area; this is a category absent from every current LIS taxonomy and justified by bibliographic, cultural, and community warrant.

Proposed additions undergo committee review against the warrant criteria above before advancing to the community feedback phase.

5. Community Feedback Process

Phase 1 – SIG Review: A draft taxonomy will be shared with chairs of all ALISE Special Interest Groups for structured feedback using a standardized form designed and administered by the committee chair.

Phase 2 – Membership Review: A revised draft incorporating SIG feedback will be opened to the full ALISE membership for comment. Feedback will be collected, synthesized, and documented by the committee.

The Board will receive the final draft accompanied by a feedback summary report documenting how community input was incorporated or addressed.

6. Linked Data Compatibility (Phase 2 Goal)

The revised taxonomy is designed with linked data compatibility in mind. Each descriptor will be assigned a stable identifier, and the full taxonomy will be structured to support future publication as **SKOS** (Simple Knowledge Organization System) linked open data – the W3C standard for publishing controlled vocabularies on the web. Full linked data publication is proposed as a recommendation for the standing committee, following formal adoption of the revised taxonomy by the ALISE Board.

7. Timeline

The committee meets monthly. The revised taxonomy must be complete and Board-ready by **December 2026** at the latest, as the ALISE Call for Proposals for the 2027 Annual Conference is expected to go out in January 2027. The revised taxonomy must be in place before that CFP is issued.

Milestone	Target Date
Inaugural meeting – methodology and process agreed	May 2026
Committee completes draft taxonomy	August 2026
SIG Chairs feedback – Phase 1	September 2026
Membership feedback – Phase 2	October 2026
Final revision by committee	November 2026
Final draft submitted to ALISE Board	December 2026

Deadline note: The revised taxonomy must be submitted to the ALISE Board by December 2026 to be in place before the Call for Proposals for the 2027 Annual Conference, expected in January 2027.

References

Coleman, Anita S. (2026). *Updating the ALISE Research Taxonomy*. Association for Library and Information Science Education (ALISE). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20370505>

ISO 25964-1:2011. *Information and documentation — Thesauri and interoperability with other vocabularies — Part 1: Thesauri for information retrieval*. International Organization for Standardization.

ISO 25964-2:2013. *Information and documentation — Thesauri and interoperability with other vocabularies — Part 2: Interoperability with other vocabularies*. International Organization for Standardization.

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